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Exploring Discipline Strategies of Pakistani Parents: A Qualitative Study
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ABSTRACT

The current study examined the discipline strategies of Pakistani parents. To gain insight into parental discipline strategies, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 20 participants. The age range of participants was from 18 to 25 years, and these participants were all raised by Pakistani parents. The findings of this study resulted in seven super themes that are: 1) Corporal Punishment & Harsh Discipline, 2) Positive & Negative Approaches in Parenting, 3) Parental Favoritism & Biasness, 4) Influence of Family Dynamics, 5) Impact of Digital & Non-Balanced Approach, 6) Parenting Challenges & Needs, and 7) Parent-Child Emotional Disconnection. The findings of the current study highlighted that many Pakistani parents used harsh discipline strategies such as corporal punishment, verbal reprimand, withholding food, locking in a dark room, and emotional neglect. Such strategies often created fear, communication barriers, and led children to hide their true feelings and matters, causing long-term emotional distress. Whereas this study also revealed positive strategies such as positive reinforcement, appreciation, and open communication, however, these were less commonly used. Moreover, positive strategies to discipline encourage parent-child relationships and give positive outcomes. The findings of this study highlight how discipline strategies of Pakistani parents are influenced by cultural norms, parental stress, and lack of awareness about healthy and positive discipline strategies.

Keywords: Parental Discipline, Parenting Approach, Discipline Strategies, Child Behavior Regulation, Pakistani Parents, Thematic Analysis, Cultural Context

INTRODUCTION

Child growth or the upbringing of a child is influenced by the parenting, which is one of the most important factors in child development (Awiszus et al., 2022). Children show both positive and negative behaviors, which are linked to the parenting style and discipline strategies used by parents (Folaranmi, 2025). According to the study by Purnama et al. (2022), children's behavioral issues and behavioral challenges are worldwide issues. These issues and challenges are often caused by parenting styles that parents use to discipline their child, because child behaviors are mostly linked with parenting styles (Purnama et al., 2022).

According to Lanjekar et al. (2022), there are four types of parenting styles: authoritative parenting, authoritarian parenting, permissive parenting, and uninvolved parenting. In each parenting style, parents have different demands and responses from their children; each style

has different effects on children's behavior and emotional health, depending on the style used by parents (Pal & Verma, 2024). In authoritative parenting, parents prefer positive discipline strategies that involve guidance, open communication, and logical consequences rather than harsh punishments (Pal & Verma, 2024). Authoritarian parents use harsh and punitive discipline strategies to discipline their children. The study by Lanjekar et al. (2022) found that parents often use punishments as a tool to correct behavior and rarely prefer open discussion with their children. The study by Pal & Verma (2024) found that a permissive parenting style, parents adopt a lenient approach to discipline their children. The study by Lanjekar et al. (2022) found that uninvolved parents show negligence or absence of discipline.

Discipline strategies that are used by parents can have short-term and long-term effects on children like the way parents disciplining can cause effects on child's academic performance, on their interpersonal skills and as well as on their mental health (Sarwar, 2016). Many aspects of parenting are impactful, but parents' discipline strategies are one of the most effective aspects for children's coping mechanisms, shaping behaviors, social relationships, and emotional regulation (Gershoff et al., 2010). According to the study by Salari et al. (2014), behavioral problems of children are positively linked with ineffective parental discipline strategies. It means that more ineffective strategies can cause more behavioral issues, fewer use of ineffective strategies causes fewer behavioral issues in a child (Salari et al., 2014).

Mostly, parents use harsh discipline strategies, in which physical punishment and psychological torture are involved, such as hitting them physically, kicking, shaking the child, and yelling at them (UNICEF, 2024). Corporal punishment or physical punishment can be defined as punishment that is used to reduce or eliminate undesirable behavior of a child or to alter the behavior (Avezum et al., 2023). In this type of punishment, physical force is used to cause discomfort or pain to the child (Visser et al., 2022). The study by Durrant and Ensom (2012) shows that corporal punishment is highly associated with increasing the level of aggression in children, negative mental health outcomes, and developmental harm. The study by M.-T. Wang and Kenny (2014) show that harsh verbal discipline strategies negatively affect children's mental health. Positive parenting is defined as the parenting characterized by warmth, providing support, setting boundaries, and respectful communication with the child (Su et al., 2022). The study by L. Zhang et al. (2024) found that emotional warmth can reduce many behavioral problems.

The study by Akhtar et al. (2017) shows that children's emotional attachment and closeness with their grandparents provide help to protect children from the negative outcomes of their parents' parenting. The study by Y. Li et al. (2019) found parents' care is less associated with less externalizing issues, and grandparental care and overprotection are highly associated with more issues in children, such as emotional problems and behavioral issues.

Social media and digital technology are shaping modern parenting. The study by Olpin et al. (2023) found that parents use social media for knowledge instead of enjoyment or fun; those parents are more confident during parenting. Social media helps them to improve communication and achieve better emotional well-being. A study by Wong et al. (2020) found that excessive use of phones or tablets and excessive parents' screen time resulted in a decrease in interaction between parents and their children. Another study by P. Zhang & Wang (2025), parents focusing on mobile while ignoring their child, highly associated with more conflicts, negative emotional outcomes, and social withdrawal.

Pakistan's cultural values and beliefs still support harsh discipline strategies such as corporal punishment (Ashraf & Holden, 2022). According to the study by Zaman et al. (2014), discipline methods are different across cultures, and in Pakistan's culture, authoritarian parenting styles

are still commonly used by parents to discipline their children. According to another study by Zaman et al. (2014), many Pakistani parents often consider control, obedience, and moral upbringing to discipline their children. Normalization and acceptance of harsh discipline strategies such as corporal punishment by parents and children is still common in Pakistan (UNICEF Pakistan, 2022). Most existing studies in Pakistan have focused on parenting styles and their effects through quantitative studies, leaving a gap in understanding the personal, emotional, and justificatory experiences associated with different discipline strategies. There is a lack of qualitative studies on exploring how disciplinary strategies are perceived and experienced by those who grew up under them. The current study aims to explore how Pakistani parents' discipline strategies shape children's emotional well-being, behavior, and parent-child relationships, and how these strategies are perceived and experienced by young adults.

METHOD

Research Design

The current study used a qualitative approach with reflexive thematic analysis as its research method and data analysis technique (Braun & Clarke, 2006). To explore the discipline strategies of Pakistani parents through young adults' perspectives and their experience with parents' discipline strategies.

Participants

The current study included a total 20 number of young adults, with an age range of participants between 18 and 25 years. The age range was mature enough to reflect their childhood experiences and also able to recall those experiences in detail. In this qualitative research, the sample size of 20 was deemed adequate because data saturation in an interview-based research is usually achieved after 12 to 20 interviews (Guest et al., 2006).

Inclusion Criteria and Exclusion Criteria

- Participants aged 18 to 25 years who had been brought up by Pakistani parents, as well as those who had undergone parental discipline measures, were included.
- The participants had to be capable of reflecting on their experiences, speaking either Urdu or English, and participating voluntarily. • Persons under the age of 18 years or over 25 years were not included.
- Those who were not brought up by their biological parents or their primary caregivers were excluded.
- Participants with extreme psychiatric or cognitive illnesses that may compromise the ability to recall were excluded.
- Those who did not want to be audio-recorded or have their interviews transcribed were not included.

Measures

In the current qualitative research, the researcher's role served as the primary data collection instrument, a creative embodiment of the methodology that brings personal insight and depth to the study. For the investigation and data collection, a semi-structured interview was designed to explore young adults' experiences of discipline strategies that were used by their parents.

Procedure

The study explores the discipline strategies of Pakistani parents through young adults' perspectives and their experiences of parental discipline strategies. It involves 20 young adults, selected purposefully, and uses a qualitative approach employing reflexive thematic analysis as its research method and data analysis technique. After obtaining informed consent and

ensuring confidentiality, data were collected through semi-structured interviews with participants. The current study analyzed participants' responses using qualitative methods and expressed gratitude to participants for their cooperation.

Validity and Reliability of the Study

Validity and reliability in this study were also ensured through a structured research process and expert review. A three-member review committee, including the research supervisor, the researcher, and a peer reviewer, reviewed the interview guide, research procedures, and identified themes to ensure clarity, relevance, and accurate representation of participants' experiences. The credibility of the findings was enhanced by semi-structured interviews, which provided a rich and detailed exploration of views. The same interview and analysis process was followed for all participants, and the committee also reviewed the coding and themes to ensure consistency. It also strengthened the dependability and trustworthiness of the study findings.

Data Analysis

Thematic analysis has been used to analyze the collected data, to find common patterns, and to find key themes from the transcriptions of conducted interviews. Thematic analysis, including a six-phase framework (Braun & Clarke, 2006), is productive for identifying patterns, and researchers obtain themes that help to represent individuals' shared meanings and individual differences. The data was carefully coded by the researcher and categorized to organize different discipline strategies, the effectiveness of such discipline strategies, and the challenges that are faced by parents. Thematic analysis approach based on the following six steps to analyze the data (Braun & Clarke, 2006):

- 1. Familiarization with the data:** Data familiarization means reading and re-reading collected data, reading multiple times interview transcriptions to fully understand participants' points of view. This first step helped researchers to focus on important things in the data, such as the important ideas and emotions of participants.
- 2. Generating initial codes:** For generating codes, researchers go through the data and then highlight the important ideas or label key parts that were important for the study, and those parts' ideas that were repeated, these labels know the code that has basic ideas.
- 3. Searching for themes:** After generating codes, group similar codes into themes and subthemes. In this step, a group of similar codes is picked and forms themes.
- 4. Reviewing themes:** In this step, check themes and refine them, and check if the generated themes are related to the data. At this stage, some themes were combined, some were changed, and some were eliminated or removed.
- 5. Defining and naming themes:** In this step, define each generated theme's meanings and give them a suitable name, which helps to explain how themes relate to the study's questions.
- 6. Producing the report:** In this step, the final write-up started, and themes connecting to literature or previous studies and research questions were generated and explained with examples from collected data.

RESULTS

Thematic analysis was conducted for the results of the current study based on discipline strategies of Pakistani parents (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The data for the current study were collected through semi-structured interviews of young adults. Interviews were transcribed, and transcriptions of participants' interviews were read multiple times for the data familiarization step. Firstly, codes were generated, and these codes were grouped into themes and then

themes into super themes. The themes were revealing parents' discipline strategies and their effects on children's well-being. Corrections and refinements were made in the results after the study completion to enhance the presentation and reliability of the findings.

Table 1: Super Themes and Themes related to the study Exploring Discipline Strategies of Pakistani Parents (N=20)

Super Themes	Themes
<i>Corporal Punishment & Harsh Discipline</i>	Forms of corporal punishment Psychological effects of corporal punishment Myths about corporal punishment Public discipline negative effects Negative forms of punishment Negative effects of punishment Harsh discipline strategies Negative effects of harsh disciplining Normalization of harsh discipline strategies
<i>Positive & Negative Approaches in Parenting</i>	Forms of appreciation Effectiveness of appreciation Positive forms of punishment Positive effects of punishment Parents showing their love Other positive things in parenting Effectiveness of positive strategies Mothers' positive ways Fathers' positive ways Fathers' negative ways Other negative strategies in parenting Negative effects of other negative strategies in parenting
<i>Parental Favoritism & Biasness</i>	Parents' favoritism towards one Gender based parental favoritism Gender based parental biasness Effects of parental differences Forms of comparison Side effects of child comparison
<i>Influence of Family Dynamics</i>	Parental role in extended member's parenting Positivity of extended family members Negative effects of extended member's parenting Negative effects of parent's fights Negative effects of parents prioritizing others
<i>Impact of Digital & Non- Balanced Approach</i>	Positive effects of parents' mobile use Negative effects of parents' mobile use Negative effects of over-screening Side effects of over-caring Negative effects of over-leniency

<p><i>Parenting Challenges & Needs</i></p>	<p>Impact of high expectations Parents challenges in parenting Strategies instead of harsh disciplining Strategies to control screen time Need of strategies in parenting Desiring strategies in parenting Parents regrets Factors effects parenting</p>
<p><i>Parent-Child Emotional Disconnection</i></p>	<p>Emotionally distance in parenting Impact of constant complains or criticism Impact of parents distrusting child</p>

Figure 1: The Thematic Model based on the Super Themes and Themes of Discipline strategies of Pakistani Parents

Presented with xmind

1. Corporal Punishment & Harsh Discipline

Corporal Punishment & Harsh discipline captures young adults' experiences and observations of corporal punishment or physical punishment and any other strict or harsh discipline strategies that were used by their parents. This super theme consists of 9 themes described below:

Forms of corporal punishment

According to the participants, many parents used corporal punishment to discipline their children; parents give physical pain to children by hitting them, parents often slap a child, use hangers, slippers, belts, and sticks for hitting. Participants reported that parents mostly use any accessible objects and often give physical punishment immediately.

A participant explained that:

“I have been hit with slippers... by both mother and father and... I have also been slapped and... have been beaten with a stick” (P 9, DU 42).

Psychological effects of corporal punishment

Participants reported about the negative impact of corporal punishment on children, which negatively affects their mental health, self-esteem, and generates suicidal thoughts. It also affects social skills and emotional health.

A participant explained that:

"I have misbehaved with my mother. At that time, I left the house and went to the park, then I came back, so... and again, the second time means at the same time, firstly I said at home that I will leave the house... then I came back. After this, I just lay down. Everyone was sleeping outside, the whole night I was alone lying and watching outside the door, thinking that the death angel would come and I would die, so now I didn't want to live because that one slap, because it happened rarely, so when it happened it felt like the world was ending. So whenever I got slapped, I used to stay upset for one to two weeks... my mood off for one to two weeks, then I have not talked to anyone, have not eaten a meal" (P 3, DU 42).

Myths about corporal punishment

Participants also described some societies' myths about corporal punishments, such as many people consider corporal punishment makes a child strong or increases a child's strength, and consider corporal punishment as the only strategy to discipline children.

A participant explained that:

"Mothers are enough, they are psychologists and their only technique and strategy is hitting, this is treatment for every problem of a child" (P 1, DU 194).

Public discipline negative effects

According to the participants, many parents discipline their children publicly by using harsh discipline strategies. Many participants reported the negative effects of public disciplining. It causes social judgment fears, affects social skills, and lowers self-esteem. Publicly disciplining is ineffective and causes aggression, rebellion, and affects mental health. A participant explained that:

"Even today, my self-esteem still fluctuates, so it's not strong enough for me to talk in front of everyone, because I have this fear that if I do something wrong, my mother will glare at me and insult me in front of everyone" (P 8, DU 46).

Negative forms of punishment

Participants described negative types of punishments, such as skipping a child's lunch or dinner, emotionally neglecting the child, locking the child in a dark, isolating the child for a long time, kicking the child out of the home as punishment, or stopping the child's studies as punishment.

A participant explained that:

"They used to lock us in the room... turning the lights off, making it dark... They locked us like this... They didn't hit us that much, but when they got very aggressive, then they used to lock us in the room, saying that... this is your punishment, now you have to stay inside for half an hour or an hour, not come outside" (P 17, DU 66).

Negative effects of punishment

Participants described the negative outcomes of harsh punishments. Locking a child in a dark room causes fear; excessive boycotting of the child causes the child to question their own worth. It is also associated with trauma and affects mental health.

A participant explained that:

"Child locked in a room, make it dark, and he is afraid of darkness, then I say it will leave an impact on his mind and psyche for lifelong that he will still be afraid of darkness. If you turn off the lights, he will still be afraid that he has been locked in the room" (P 17, DU 68).

Harsh discipline strategies

Participants described harsh discipline strategies, such as physical punishment when a child doesn't know about the mistake, using extreme physical violence, zero human margin, disciplining publicly, criticizing, taunting the child, or being harsh on unmet expectations.

A participant explained that:

"They never explained... always just scolded... explaining is far from it, they only scolded... and did nothing else" (P 17, DU 50).

Negative effects of harsh disciplining

Participants explained that harsh parenting associated with childhood trauma often imposes their traumas on others. It is associated with negative traits in children, it encourages the intergenerational cycle, also negatively affecting communication, social skills, and parent-child relationships.

A participant explained that:

"I didn't share my matters with my mother... arranged on my own... Mostly, I had to hide my matters because if she knew then... then the same... anger... scolding these things" (P 16, DU 164).

Normalization of harsh discipline strategies

Some participants consider corporal punishment to be normal, commonly used, and important. Harsh discipline strategies are culturally accepted in Pakistan, and such traditional strategies are commonly used in many houses.

A participant explained that:

"I guess until he does not feel pain... say it like, until he does not feel bodily... that I did something wrong... means if only told then... It doesn't have the same effect, here the point is about effect, when pain is felt only then it works" (P 12, DU 38).

2. Positive & Negative Approaches in Parenting

Positive & Negative Approaches in Parenting captures parents' positive strategies for child disciplining and other negative methods, except harsh methods like corporal punishment, and parents' approaches that didn't include any physical punishment. This super theme consists of 12 themes described below:

Forms of appreciation

Participants described parents' different ways of appreciation after good behavior, such as giving rewards or gifts, publicly appreciating children, and often taking the child for an outing.

A participant explained that:

"I used to get praise, even get rewards from father in the form of money, and from mother... mother takes me for shopping or mother gives me too many compliments every time... this thing made me feel proud" (P 15, DU 126).

Effectiveness of appreciation

Participants explained the effectiveness of appreciation, such as increasing motivation, and positively reinforcing the child's targeted behavior. It increases confidence and decreases the level of mistakes.

A participant explained that:

"I guess children will be more motivated to do better, they feel that I do this work, so my mother and father praise me, then they receive a kind of reinforcement as appreciation, so I think they will be more motivated" (P 1, DU 134).

Positive forms of punishment

Participants described positive punishments to discipline children, such as cutting pocket money or negative reinforcement, punishing privately, hand-raising, or rooster postures.

A participant explained that:

“One was that pocket money used to be cut, the second was that... they didn’t talk to us, father had an issue that he wouldn’t talk, mother had an issue she wouldn’t talk to us. Then we used to say sorry in front of everyone then they would forgive us. This boycott issue was the greatest fear for us that if the mother got upset, these morals... this was important for moral development” (P 8, DU 60).

Positive effects of punishment

Participants described the effectiveness of positive punishments, such as modifying target behavior. Positive or healthy punishments are effective for children's discipline without any harmful outcomes.

A participant explained that:

“If I give punishment to a child, he knows that this mistake I should not repeat because I will get punished for it. That’s why we... should punish a child, it’s better than beating and... it’s better than scolding, that gives him a little punishment... so, before the mistake means... the child understands that. I should not make this mistake” (P 6, DU 80).

Parents showing their love

Many participants stated that parents not showing their love directly or verbally, although parents show love by looking after, giving gifts, fulfilling the child’s needs or wishes.

A participant explained that:

“Mother is a little bit expressive, she says it out, Father is... like gifts or something like this... through favours or provides you with something new, this is his way of expressing love” (P 7, DU 84).

Other positive strategies in parenting

Participants explained many other positive methods, such as treating children equally, balancing every approach, and both parents play their roles in upbringing. Parents don’t channel their stress on children, encouraging open communication and autonomy, trusting the child's decisions, and setting clear boundaries.

A participant explained that:

“We have given all kinds of freedom, but with clear limits that we could not cross, and... and we are happy within that freedom. We have gatherings with our family of every kind, we laugh and play with our parents, they also do means it’s like... friendly environment and also give us freedom. We are also allowed to go out with friends, but have to inform, follow the given time limit, but we can go and enjoy, but within limits” (P 2, DU 100).

Effectiveness of positive strategies

Participants described effectiveness of positive strategies, such as modifying targeted behaviors and open communication, can decrease the level of mistakes. Children learn from parents’ positive behaviors, such as behaving similarly to others. When parents give respect to their child, it enhances courage. Many parents are lenient in a balanced way, which can increase confidence and decision-making.

A participant explained that:

“The parents’ trust that, they know that their child will not speak a lie, and they know that their child will not steal. This parent’s trust that they know I will not do this, it stops us at many places from performing wrong actions” (P 3, DU 192).

Mothers’ positive ways

Participants reported that many mothers express their love directly by physical or verbal affection. While others show their love indirectly, such as by cooking favorite meals, being polite, friendly, and supporting as a friend.

A participant explained that:

“Mothers are very gentle, very polite, my mother never beat us, never questioned us on anything... like she... always takes my opinions” (P 5, DU 30).

Fathers’ positive ways

Many participants reported that fathers express their love indirectly, such as by fulfilling needs or guiding, while some fathers showed their love directly by physical or verbal affection.

A participant explained that:

“Father is a little bit different, when... he wants to express love, then he gives us a lecture... like this is his way to show his concern that he cares a lot about us, he thinks about us. Apart from this, something our favorite like he knows that we... what more prefer to eat, often he brings those things when he comes back home” (P 5, DU 108).

Fathers’ negative ways

Participants explained that mostly fathers deal aggressively, do not prioritize their own children, and impose expectations on children.

A participant explained that:

“Father is also strict, like in times he showed strictness, he is very strict and... he is strict in his opinions” (P 5, DU 32)

Other negative strategies in parenting

Participants reported that many parents constantly complain, criticize children, and release their frustration on them. Many parents do not explain the logic behind restrictions.

A participant explained that:

“They used to explain to me afterwards, firstly they got aggressive, then they hit and beat, etc, then after this they used to explain” (P 14, DU 69).

Negative effects of other negative strategies in parenting

Participants reported that children start negatively comparing their parents. Parents’ negative judgments can cause communication barriers. When parents do not support their children, it can make the child rebellious.

A participant explained that:

“Am telling Mama that the boy is watching me at that time, if my mother replies to me that what you have done, that he was watching you, why he was watching only you, why not watching others, it must be your fault, did you wear dupata or not” (P 3, DU 48).

3. Parental Favoritism & Biasness

Parental Favoritism & Biasness highlights the parents’ favoritism for one child, such as for the elder or the younger one, and the methods of parents to discipline them also differ from those methods that are used for all children. This super theme consists of 6 themes described below:

Parents’ favoritism towards one

Many participants reported that parents showed favoritism towards one child among all the children, such as favoritism towards the elder child or the younger child.

A participant explained that:

“Some parents give too much attention to their children, give very much, and some, it’s not like that in our case, not giving that much attention, they are mostly focused on their own matters. Some children... like my eldest sister receive a lot of attention, eldest brother also receives a lot... it can be said that I didn’t get any attention for what I am doing, how I am, or what I am, they don’t care” (P 6, DU 120).

Gender based parental favoritism

Participants reported that many parents show leniency and provide more to their sons, while imposing excessive restrictions on their daughters. Many participants reported that mothers

show more love and care for their son, while fathers show more love and care towards their daughter.

A participant explained that:

"My father loves me a lot, also loves his sons, but loves me more; this thing is natural, that fathers love daughters more and mothers love sons more" (P 17, DU 92).

Gender based parental biasness

Many participants reported that parents provide more to sons and less to daughters. Parents show leniency to their sons and strictness to their daughters, show unconditional love for sons, and do not even take any stand on sons' big mistakes.

A participant explained that:

"If something went wrong with the daughter, then parents used to say that it's the daughter's fault, and if the son did something wrong, then parents used to say its ok, young blood used to this. If a boy does a love marriage, then it's ok, but if a girl does, then she is tarnishing the family's name" (P 3, DU 254).

Effects of parental differences

Many participants reported that many children perceived this difference and complained to their parents. It can cause conflicts and jealousy among siblings, an inferiority complex, and rebellion.

A participant explained that:

"In children, effects show that one child feels like he is inferior, while other children feel that he did everything for his parent. It often causes conflict between children and creates misunderstandings between both children, which harms their future relations" (P 11, DU 182).

Forms of comparison

Many participants reported that their parents compare them with their siblings, with other children, and some compare their child with everyone.

A participant explained that:

"They compare with outsiders, mostly with friends' sons, with neighbours and... often compare with everyone" (P 13, DU 142).

Side effects of child comparison

Many participants reported that excessive comparison can negatively affect creativity and growth, and it can cause a gap between parents and children. Comparison affects mental health, lowers confidence and self-esteem, and leads to rebellious behavior.

A participant explained that:

"Sometimes it hurt me because when I was little, I was helpless, I couldn't react, so that sense of comparison still exists in me, which means I... unintentionally, un. consciously, without wanting to, still am doing that... should I do this? Did my sister do this or not? then I should not do, even if I really want to do, but I avoid doing certain things because my sister didn't do these things. So, like this, your self-esteem and confidence automatically become low, so that comparison is a very harmful thing, it should not be done" (P 8, DU 98).

4. Influence of Family Dynamics

The super theme "Influence of Family Dynamics" highlights the role of other family members in a child's upbringing. This super theme consists of 5 themes described below:

Parental role in extended member's parenting

Participants reported that parents allow extended members to discipline publicly, allowing others to use harsh discipline strategies.

A participant explained that:

“My uncle used to beat me, and my mother was not able to say anything because we were at my uncle’s place, so my mother got upset, but mother used to stay quiet and said that it’s ok, he is my uncle, and she is also a stubborn child. But my mother used to get upset, and they also used to give me punishments, not my parents gave that much. My brother grabbed my mobile, isolated me, and... gave me a warning that not allowed to go to school, college, or university, this type of warning” (P 9, DU 60).

Positivity of extended family members

Participants explained that elder siblings protect children from parental harsh discipline. Grandparents and other family members also protect the child and provide emotional warmth.

A participant explained that:

“Like our father and mother have a fight... then elder siblings take us on side, or they used to say that it’s ok, it happens, or. Parents are not fighting; that is love. Because elder siblings have faced these things, they know how it feels, so they want us to never face those things” (P 10, DU 40).

Negative effects of extended members’ parenting

Participants reported that other members’ harsh disciplining causes more negative effects on the child’s mental health. It can spoil the child and weaken the parents’ authority.

A participant explained that:

“Whenever I become stubborn on little things, then my uncle used to hold me and lock me in the washroom... make darkness, turn off the lights. Today, I still can’t forget these things and think that’s why they did this to me, it has a negative impact” (P 9, DU 60).

Negative effects of parents’ fights

Participants stated that parents who fight too much and have intense fights cause emotional withdrawal and fear. It also negatively affects social skills and causes isolation.

A participant explained that:

“We are still not forgetting this thing is more than enough. that I still remember my childhood, when parents used to fight, when they used to say harsh words to each other or. When... that means my childhood was full of stress. I am telling you, I have seen too many fights and conflicts in my childhood, even though I have experienced my parents’ separation” (P 9, DU 132).

Negative effects of parents prioritizing others

Participants reported that when parents prioritize others, it lowers self-esteem, causes hurtful feelings, aggression, and jealousy.

A participant explained that:

“When they prioritize them and ignore us, then I feel a little upset... that we should get the same priority as others... priority should be given that is necessary” (P 14, DU 218).

5. Impact of Digital & Non- Balanced Approach

Impact of Digital & Non-Balanced Approach captures the role of social media in parenting and the effects of social media on parenting. It also highlights the impact of parents’ over-leniency and care, and outcomes appear when parents do not use balanced approaches. This super theme consists of 6 themes described below:

Positive effects of parents’ mobile use

Participants reported that parents learn positive strategies from social media platforms, such as becoming more friendly and giving autonomy to their children.

A participant explained that:

“If my mother is using her mobile, then she is learning productive things that bring change in her. I asked her where she got this from, and she replied, ‘I listened to it on my mobile.’ It feels

very good to see her change, so I guess social media is productive for parents...they pick good things, not bad ones" (P 9, DU 158).

Negative effects of parents' mobile use

Participants reported that parents give less attention to their children and compare their children. It also causes fears in parents.

A participant explained that:

"In a way, social media... has become a close circle where you have access to everything. When you have access, the information is also available to you. When information is available, you know the comparison increases too much. Like this person doing this, that person doing this, and you are here" (P 7, DU 210).

Negative effects of over-screening

Many participants reported that parents introduced screens at an early age. It causes frustration in children, increases aggression levels, and jealousy.

A participant explained that:

"The more phone is given to the child, the more he becomes ill-mannered, and keeps becoming" (P 6, DU 272).

Side effects of over-caring

Participants reported that over-caring causes hurdles in the child's growth, making the child weaker and delayed than other children of the same age group.

A participant explained that:

"They care more than actually needed, which means that... consistent over-caring...especially with boys. this thing is harmful. and I noticed symptoms of that in myself ... I had to face a lot of problems because of it...There were many things in me that should have improved much earlier but, these things started getting better just now" (P 18, DU 38).

Negative effects of over-leniency

Participants described that too much leniency spoils children, and disrespecting others.

A participant explained that:

"Those children on whom less strictness is applied, they respond to their parents in an ill-mannered way" (P 1, DU 82).

Impact of high expectations

Participants reported that excessive expectations can cause isolation, limit the child's creativity, mindset, and growth.

A participant explained that:

"I am the eldest one, expectations are high from me, and I have very little chance of errors if there is no margin. So, sometimes I want that like I should have gone to the background and sit there, nothing happening from me... now I'm just sitting on the side" (P 5, DU 144).

6. Parenting Challenges & Needs

Parenting Challenges & Needs highlights the challenges and hurdles that parents mostly face. It also highlights the needs that are important for child upbringing, but are mostly not practiced by parents. This super theme consists of 7 themes described below:

Parents' challenges in parenting

Many participants reported on parental challenges such as understand child's behavior and tantrums, giving autonomy, dealing with traditional beliefs and societal judgments, maintaining equality, and managing multiple things.

A participant explained that:

"When children start making big decisions in their lives, then here is the big challenge for parents that how to explain to the child what is better for him or how to accept his likes. So,

according to me, this is a big challenge, apart from that... if something happens to children, this also could be a big challenge" (P 11, DU 198).

Strategies instead of harsh disciplining

Participants reported that fear-based control can be used over hitting, disciplining a child by explaining verbally and politely about mistakes. Parents can use situational disciplining, don't discipline the child publicly; use levels of discipline. Use positive punishments, such as positive and negative reinforcements.

A participant explained that:

"In childhood, they developed our habit of teeth brushing at night in a way that my brother and I used to keep an eye on each other. They told us that whoever catches that other sibling who went to sleep without brushing teeth, tell me the next day, and that person's pocket money who skips brushing will be given to the one who catches" (P 8, DU 60).

Strategies to control screen time

Participants reported that parents can use toys, enhance children's physical activity by providing accessories, take the child for an outing, enhance their social skills, and improve their physical health. Set a time limit for mobile use, and make sure they use the mobile in a productive way.

A participant explained that:

"You should enroll your child in such institutes where he can learn at least a little skill. Nowadays, people send their children to swimming classes and... writing, if not for writing, there are exercises to strengthen the grip of their hands, there are a lot of things, you should invest in your child... so that when your child grows up, he can realize how those things had a positive impact on him. Mobiles are important, I don't say they aren't, children also develop good learning through them... Now, it's YouTube or something else; there's privacy, you can select which channels your child watches and for how long, and set timings for your child. Also invest on your child in good curricular activities, then you will clearly see the difference in your children." (P 16, DU 200).

Need of strategies in parenting

Participants described the need to maintain balance while using any kind of discipline strategy; both parents' involvement is necessary for child upbringing. Parents should explain to children the mistakes that they know the child can make.

A participant explained:

"Give time to your children and... like... listen to them rather than telling them, and if you have to explain them something then... don't explain me by saying it happens, give them logic for that, because nowadays time is not like that, you say anything to children and they accept it quietly. They are doing counter questioning and asking reasons, so if you want, they efficiently take actions, then give them reasons for those logical reasons for that" (P7, DU 240).

Desiring strategies in parenting

Many participants reported that they wished their parents would use positive discipline strategies instead of harsh strategies. They wished their parents to give them time, attention, and love, and to be emotionally expressive and show affection to their children.

A participant explained that:

"So, I guess it was quite extreme. Mother should explain it with love, that if I refuse you for this thing, then there must be a reason behind it. So, I guess she should have used that technique or strategy, but her mother used extreme hitting" (P 1, DU 40).

Parents' regrets

According to many respondents, parents also regret being overly lenient and often regret it after seeing the negative impact on their children.

A participant explained that:

"They regret it, which means that father doesn't express... he rarely speaks, it's his nature. Mother regrets that she did this, and she used to say sorry to us" (P 12, DU 36).

Factors effects parenting

Many participants reported that our society and areas also affect parenting, and parents' education also has an impact on parenting.

A participant explained that: *"Because my father is well-educated than my mother, so today we still see the difference, that when one well-educated person becomes a father or mother, then he/she never allows society pressure to come on children, he/she has enough bravery and strength that can stop society pressure" (P 8, DU 134).*

7. Parent-Child Emotional Disconnection

Parent-Child Disconnection highlights the impact of parents' constant complaining, criticizing, taunting on children, and some parents are emotionally disconnected from their children. This super theme consists of 3 themes described below:

Emotionally distance in parenting

Many participants reported that parents are not giving enough attention and time to their children, a lack of parental support, and a communication barrier. There is a lack of both physical and verbal affection.

A participant explained that:

"They never express, my mother and father never express to their children how much they love them, definitely they do, we are their children, so, but... they never use... or never give us hope that we are important to them" (P 17, DU 134).

Impact of constant complaints or criticism

Many respondents described that constant complaining is ineffective for disciplining the child, as it lowers confidence, increases aggression, and affects a child's psychological well-being.

A participant explained that:

"Nowadays, I can even say that their words are more effective for us than their slaps... their words hurt most. Mostly those taunts... given by mother or father... it hurts a lot, and the person starts thinking Why did they say? Why did they say this? Whole night that person will not sleep, person... will keep thinking. why they said these words, and why I gave them the opportunity to say this... they used to trust me, why I broke their trust" (P 9, DU 56).

Impact of parents' distrusting child

Participants reported that parental distrust negatively affects psychological and emotional well-being.

A participant explained that:

"It hurts me a lot, I went silent, I didn't say anything, I picked up stuff quietly and went inside" (P 3, DU 80).

DISCUSSION

This study's findings and their relation to existing literature offer insights that address research questions and objectives, and suggest future research directions.

The current study aims to explore the discipline strategies of Pakistani parents through young adults' perspectives, who have experienced such discipline strategies from their parents. Different ways are used by parents for giving corporal punishment, such as using objects (Ganapathy et al., 2022), slapping, and pinching the child (Kumaraswamy & Othman, 2011).

Corporal punishment increases aggression (Lansford et al., 2014) and causes negative mental health outcomes (Fergusson et al., 2008). There are myths about corporal punishment enhancing a child's character, and hitting is the only discipline strategy that a child can understand (Jarrett, 2015). Many parents discipline their children publicly, which is often linked with the child's emotional harm (Schrobsdorff, 2015). Parents use some unhealthy punishments, such as food as punishment (Dolan, 2024). Food punishment causes negative effects on emotional well-being (Dolan, 2024), and parental punishments also cause higher feelings of loneliness (Luo et al., 2021). Most of the parents prefer to use harsh discipline strategies (UNICEF, 2024). Harsh discipline strategies are highly linked with negative mental health outcomes (Ma & Song, 2023). Normalization and acceptance of harsh discipline strategies are still common in Pakistan (UNICEF Pakistan, 2022).

Parents praise the child's positive behavior, give privileges and gifts to the child (Pensak & PhD, 2024). Appreciation improve child's well-being, attention, and behavior (MacMillan, 2017), and also increases confidence (Aprilaba, 2025). There are healthy punishments, such as negative reinforcement are used to reduce or eliminate unwanted behaviors by removing something desirable (Cherry, 2023). These punishments are effective for the target behavior, or can modify the target behavior (Larzelere et al., 2023). Many parents show love by giving gifts, spending quality time, and expressing verbally (Dewar, 2023). Many parents used a balanced approach characterized by clear boundaries (Dewar, 2023; Kirby & PhD, n.d.), used parental warmth (Y. Liu et al., 2024), and open parent-child communication (Riesch et al., 2006). It enhances the child's emotional health, social skills, and problem-solving skills (Dewar, 2023; Kirby & PhD, n.d.). Parental warmth boosts self-efficacy, motivation, and attention (Y. Liu et al., 2024), and open communication reduces risk factors in the child (Riesch et al., 2006). Mothers' open communication makes the child less afraid of making mistakes (Peterson et al., 2025). Active fathers' involvement reduces behavioral difficulties and improves mental health (Sarkadi et al., 2008). Often, parents use strict rules and harsh parenting without parental warmth and reasoning, which affects social skills and well-being (Cherry, 2025). Over-controlling and overprotective parenting negatively affects mental health (Vigdal & Brønnick, 2022).

Often, parents unconsciously show favoritism towards elder children (Gibson, 2025). Younger children receive more favoritism than older children, causing stronger emotional effects (ScienceDaily, 2017). Mothers spend more quality time with their sons and show more physical care towards their sons (Kaushal & Muchomba, 2018), while some parents show more favoritism towards daughters (Gibson, 2025). Parental differences cause negative effects, such as less sibling closeness (Suitor et al., 2009), parental favoritism, cause conflicts among siblings, negatively affect relationship quality, affect the less-favored child's mental health (Jensen & Jorgensen-Wells, 2025), and cause long-lasting emotional issues (Gibson, 2025). Parents compare their child with other children, which negatively affects the child's self-esteem, self-perception, and social interactions (H. Liu et al., 2025). Parents who compare their one child with others cause emotional disturbance, behavioral issues, and conflicts among siblings (Jensen et al., 2018).

Extended family members' interference has positive effects, such as protecting children from negative outcomes due to their parents' parenting (Akhtar et al., 2017). It also has negative effects, such as grandparents providing over-protection highly associated with more behavioral issues in children (Y. Li et al., 2019). Parents' fights cause mental health issues and affect emotional well-being (Brock & Kochanska, 2016). Parents prioritize others and neglect or ignore their own children, which causes low self-esteem, relationship issues, and affects emotional and psychological well-being (Dray, 2025).

Parents learn from social media what to do and what not to do with their children (Lee, 2015). Parents start ignoring their child because of social media, which causes negative effects on the child's emotional and psychological well-being (P. Zhang & Wang, 2025). Children's excessive screen use affects mental health (Queensland, 2025). It can also cause a jealousy factor, negative comparison, and insecurities among children (Vaillancourt et al., 2024). Over-caring causes low self-esteem, affects mental health, and social skills (Choirunnisa et al., 2025). Extra lenient parenting increases aggression level and behavioral issues (Hinnant et al., 2016). Parents' high expectations can lower self-esteem and decrease motivation (Braucher, 2020). Parents face many challenges during disciplining such as a lack of resources and support (Christian, 2023). Child behavior problems are also a challenge for parents to understand, and children's behavioral problems are also linked with parenting stress (Neece et al., 2012). Many parents can use different strategies instead of harsh discipline, such as prioritizing empathy, consistency, and guidance (Alasadi, 2025). Parents can reduce their child's screen time by engaging in outdoor activities, which are linked with better social skills (Hinkley et al., 2018) and cause positive effects on mental health (H. Wang et al., 2023). Parenting needs parental warmth, acceptance, and support, which shows positive outcomes (Br et al., 2019). Over-controlling and over-protective parenting affects mental health (Vigdal & Brønneck, 2022). Parents who used harsh discipline strategies express regret for being harsh (Luscombe, 2016), and those who used excessive leniency were frustrated and some expressed regret (Feng & Cui, 2023).

Emotionally distant parents are physically present but fail to provide warmth and empathy; it affects mental and emotional health, and they face relationship issues (Campbell, 2023). Parents' constant complaints or criticism affects child's mood (Bonduelle et al., 2023). Parental distrust affects a child's communication and emotional well-being (Feijoo et al., 2023).

CONCLUSION

The current qualitative study discussed the discipline methods of Pakistani parents as perceived by young adults. The results show that forceful disciplinary measures such as corporal punishment, verbal reprimands, and, in other situations, deprivation of food and isolation of children were widespread. The strategies were usually terrifying and stressful instead of causing a positive behavior change. The participants also noted that they faced excessive criticism, judgment, and unrealistic expectations by their parents, which had a negative influence on their self-esteem and confidence. There was a high rate of over-controlling behaviors, such as strict rules and parents completing tasks on behalf of their children, resulting in frustration, confusion, and sometimes, rebelliousness. Many parents failed to explain rules and failed to reward their children's efforts, which also created a sense of being neglected and emotionally detached. On the whole, these methods of discipline seemed to create barriers to effective communication, decrease emotional intimacy, and inhibit the development of children's autonomy.

LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The current study included 20 young adults, which is why findings may not represent all families of Pakistan. Participants' responses may have been influenced by their memories and emotions. It emphasized only Pakistani parental discipline strategies, so results may not apply to other cultures. The study's design cannot explain long-term cause-and-effect links.

Organize programs, awareness workshops, and campaigns for parents to guide them about positive and healthy discipline methods. Both child welfare groups and policymakers should promote alternatives to harsh discipline strategies, such as positive methods. Schools can also help by organizing seminars and counseling services for parents. Future research on discipline

methods should include parents' and children's views, a large sample, and long-term tracking. Clinicians can also help families to adopt positive and healthy discipline strategies.

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